

The Influence of Coordination and Leadership Quality on Work Discipline of Employees in the Department of Food Security, Agriculture, and Fisheries in South Barito Regency

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ABSTRACT: This study aims to examine the effect of coordination and leadership quality on work discipline of employees in the Department of Food Security, Agriculture, and Fisheries in South Barito Regency. The population in this study consists of all employees of the Food Security, Agriculture, and Fisheries Department of South Barito Regency, totaling 315 individuals. As the population in this study is more than 100 individuals, a random sampling method is employed based on the Slovin formula to streamline the time and cost of the research. Data were analyzed using Multiple Regression Analysis. The results of this study are Coordination has an effect on Work Discipline of employees, Leadership quality has an effect on work discipline of employee in the Department of Food Security, Agriculture, and Fisheries in South Barito Regency.

KEYWORDS: Coordination, Leadership quality, Work discipline

INTRODUCTION

The importance of special attention to human resources in an organization, especially in the context of the Food Security, Agriculture, and Fisheries Department of South Barito Regency, is emphasized. It is stated that human resources comprise elements such as thoughts, feelings, and behaviors that can influence the success of an organization. Hasibuan (2012) asserts that coordination is an activity involving direction, integration, and coordination of management elements and subordinate tasks to achieve organizational goals. The department handles three fields of work within one Regional Apparatus Organization (SKPD), namely Food Security, Agriculture, and Fisheries. Therefore, effective coordination between these fields is considered crucial to advance the organization and achieve the established vision, mission, and goals.

Furthermore, the background highlights the lack of coordination between farmers and extension workers, which can result in the ineffectiveness of the extension workers' tasks. This also contributes to the perception of a lack of employee discipline, especially due to the implementation of attendance machines only in the office and a lack of supervision in the field. The second factor discussed is the quality of leadership as a significant influence on work discipline. Leadership is deemed to play a crucial role in achieving organizational goals by effectively and efficiently utilizing available resources. With an organizational structure consisting of employees with diverse backgrounds, the importance of leaders understanding the needs and aspirations of the organization to achieve common goals is emphasized. In general, the background underscores the need for good coordination between fields and the role of quality leadership to enhance work discipline in the Food Security, Agriculture, and Fisheries Department of South Barito Regency. Work discipline is defined as discipline in attendance, attire, working hours, and adherence to organizational rules, with the expectation that a high awareness of these rules will create a high level of work discipline among employees.

Based on the background described above, the problem formulations that can be derived are:

1. Does Coordination and Leadership Quality have a significant simultaneous effect on the Work Discipline of employees in the Department of Food Security, Agriculture, and Fisheries of South Barito Regency?
2. Do Coordination and Leadership Quality have a significant partial effect on the Work Discipline of employees in the Department of Food Security, Agriculture, and Fisheries of South Barito Regency?
3. Which variable has a dominant effect on the Work Discipline of employees in the Department of Food Security, Agriculture, and Fisheries of South Barito Regency?

LITERATURE REVIEW

a. *Human Resource Management*

Management is a process of planning, organizing, leading, and controlling the efforts of members of an organization and the utilization of other resources in those activities to ensure they are carried out in accordance with established objectives. Experts define management as both a science and an art involved in a series of interrelated activities that utilize various resources to achieve a predetermined goal. The statements of some experts are as follows: "Management is the science and art of organizing the utilization of human resources and other resources effectively and efficiently to achieve a specific goal (Malayu, 2012). Management is a process to obtain comprehensive activities efficiently and effectively with and through others. Based on the above definitions, it can be concluded that management is the science and art of organizing, planning, organizing, directing, coordinating, and supervising the process of utilizing human resources and other resources effectively and efficiently to achieve the predetermined goals of an organization.

b. *Coordination*

In an organization, every leader needs to coordinate activities among the members of the organization assigned to complete tasks. With clear information delivery, effective communication, and delegation of tasks to subordinates by managers, each individual subordinate will carry out their work in accordance with the authority granted. Without coordination, every task performed by individual employees, the company's goals will not be achieved. Hasibuan (2012:85) states that: "Coordination is the activity of directing, integrating, and coordinating management elements and the tasks of subordinates in achieving organizational goals".

Coordination is the process of integrating goals and activities in separate units (departments or functional areas) within an organization to achieve objectives efficiently and effectively (Handoko, 2012). According to G.R. Terry in Hasibuan (2012:85), coordination is a synchronized and systematic effort to provide the right amount and timing, and to direct implementation to produce a consistent and harmonious action toward predetermined goals. According to E. F. L. Brech in his book "The Principle and Practice of Management," as quoted by Handayani (2012:54), Coordination is balancing and mobilizing the team by assigning suitable locations for each task and ensuring that the activities are carried out with the necessary harmony among the team members themselves.

c. *Division of Work*

Theoretically, the goal in an organization is to achieve a common objective that individuals cannot attain on their own. Groups of two or more people working cooperatively and coordinatedly can achieve results greater than what individuals can accomplish alone. In an organization, the fundamental pillar is the principle of division of labor. The principle of division of labor implies that for an organization to succeed in its efforts to achieve its goals, it should implement division of labor. Through this division of labor, the organization aims to function effectively in the pursuit of its objectives. Division of labor involves detailing tasks and responsibilities so that each individual in the organization is accountable for carrying out a set of limited activities.

Therefore, the division of labor dramatically increases effectiveness because no one is physically capable of performing all the activities in the most complex tasks, and no one possesses all the skills required to execute various duties. Hence, it is necessary to allocate tasks into specific roles and distribute them among a number of individuals. This specialized division of labor allows individuals to learn skills and become experts in specific job functions.

d. *Discipline*

In every complex organization, each department must work in coordination so that each can produce the expected results. Coordination is the adjustment of different parts to ensure that the activities of those parts are completed on time, allowing each to contribute their efforts maximally to achieve overall results. Discipline is essential for this purpose. Rivai (2012:444) defines work discipline as a tool used by managers to communicate with employees, encouraging them to willingly change their behavior and as an effort to increase awareness and willingness to adhere to all organizational rules and social norms. In other words, discipline involves attitudes and behaviors, whether individual or group, to submit and comply with the rules of an organization. In an organization, the enforcement of rules on an individual or organizational member is managed by the leaders. Leaders are expected to apply positive discipline, meaning the implementation of rules through the awareness of their subordinates. Conversely, if leaders cannot apply positive discipline to themselves, they are unlikely to apply it to others, including their subordinates. Thus, discipline

is crucial in the process of achieving goals, serving as a determining factor in the intended goal achievement.

e. Leadership

The basic task of a leader is to motivate, guide, and supervise the work carried out by employees in each department or unit, ensuring that the work conducted by the employees achieves optimal results for the organization's goals. The leadership functions that a leader must carry out include guiding, directing, coaching, fostering work motivation, steering the organization, establishing good communication networks, implementing tasks efficiently, and leading employees toward predetermined objectives.

Therefore, leadership is essentially the ability of an individual to inspire others to work willingly towards achieving predefined goals. To focus more theoretically on the discussion of leadership techniques, this literature review incorporates leadership theories from Pamudji, complemented by relevant theories from other experts. Soewarno Handyaningrat, in his book "Introduction to the Science of Administration and Management," defines leadership as follows: "Leadership is a process in which leaders are described as giving orders or directions, guidance, or influencing the work of others in choosing and achieving predetermined or established goals." (Handyaningrat, 2012). From the above definition, it can be concluded that leadership is the ability to influence others by directing, guiding, or commanding with the aim of achieving predetermined targets. Furthermore, according to M. Karyadi in his book "Leadership," he defines leadership as: "Leadership is the art of influencing human behavior and the ability to control people in the organization so that they conform to the desired behavior of the organizational leader." (Karyadi, 2012).

f. Work Discipline

The word "discipline" itself comes from the Latin word "disciplina," which means "training or education in manners and spirituality, as well as the development of habits." This emphasizes assistance to employees in developing appropriate attitudes towards their work. Discipline is a force that develops within the individual worker, enabling them to voluntarily adapt to decisions, regulations, and high values of work and behavior (Asmiarsih, 2012).

According to Fathoni (2012), discipline is the awareness and willingness of an individual to obey all company regulations and social norms. Discipline can be understood when employees consistently arrive and leave on time, perform all their tasks well, and adhere to all company regulations and social norms. Discipline must be enforced in a company organization because without the support of good employee discipline, it is difficult for a company to achieve its goals. Based on these opinions, it can be concluded that employee work discipline is an attitude or behavior that demonstrates an individual's or a group's loyalty and obedience to the rules established by their institution or organization, whether written or unwritten, with the expectation that the work performed will be effective and efficient.

g. Hypothesis

The hypothesis proposed in this research is:

- H1 : Coordination and Leadership Quality have a significant simultaneous effect on the Work Discipline of employees in the Food Security, Agriculture, and Fisheries Department of South Barito Regency.
- H2 : Coordination and Leadership Quality have a significant partial effect on the Work Discipline of employees in the Food Security, Agriculture, and Fisheries Department of South Barito Regency.
- H3 : The variable that dominantly influences the Work Discipline of employees in the Food Security, Agriculture, and Fisheries Department of South Barito Regency is Leadership Quality.

h. Conceptual Framework

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

RESEARCH METHOD

This research is quantitative in nature, aiming to explain the causal relationships among variables through hypothesis testing. Therefore, this study falls under the category of explanatory research, which seeks to explore the potential relationships between variables or how one variable influences another. The population in this study consists of all employees of the Food Security, Agriculture, and Fisheries Department of South Barito Regency, totaling 315 individuals. As the population in this study is more than 100 individuals, a random sampling method is employed based on the Slovin formula to streamline the time and cost of the research. The data analysis method for this research utilizes descriptive statistical analysis and Multiple Regression Analysis.

Operational Definition of Variables

Based on the variables that have been identified, the operational definition formulation for this research is as follows:

a. Coordination (X1)

Coordination is the activity of directing, integrating and coordinating management elements and the work of subordinates in achieving organizational goals. The indicators are:

- X1.1 Unity of Action
- X1.2 Communication
- X1.3 Division of Work

b. Leadership Quality (X2)

Leadership is basically the ability possessed by a person to move other people to work happily to achieve predetermined goals. The indicators are:

- X2.1 Supervision.
- X2.2 Responsibilities.
- X2.3 Intelligence.
- X2.4 Firmness.
- X2.5 Self-Confidence.
- X2.5 Initiative.

c. Work Discipline (Y)

Discipline is a person's awareness and willingness to obey all company regulations and applicable social norms. The indicators are:

- Y.1 Goals and abilities
- Y.2 Leadership example
- Y.3 Remuneration/Salary
- Y.4 Justice

- Y.5 Attached supervision
- Y.6 Punishment sanctions
- Y.7 Firmness
- Y.8 Human relations

RESULT

Validity Test

Table 1. The Result of Validity Test

Variabel	Item	R Count	Keterangan
Coordination (X1)	X1.1	0,796	Valid
	X1.2	0,836	Valid
	X1.3	0,791	Valid
	X1.4	0,809	Valid
	X1.5	0,860	Valid
	X1.6	0,892	Valid
	X1.7	0,625	Valid
	X1.8	0,646	Valid
Leadership Quality (X2)	X2.1	0,363	Valid
	X2.2	0,730	Valid
	X2.3	0,754	Valid
	X2.4	0,784	Valid
	X2.5	0,731	Valid
	X2.6	0,701	Valid
	X2.7	0,814	Valid
	X2.8	0,745	Valid
	X2.9	0,841	Valid
	X2.10	0,840	Valid
	X2.11	0,850	Valid
	X2.12	0,837	Valid
	X2.13	0,821	Valid
	X2.14	0,827	Valid
	X2.15	0,815	Valid
	X2.16	0,810	Valid
	X2.17	0,793	Valid
	X2.18	0,797	Valid
Work Discipline (Y)	Y.1	0,687	Valid
	Y.2	0,738	Valid
	Y.3	0,774	Valid
	Y.4	0,664	Valid
	Y.5	0,627	Valid
	Y.6	0,645	Valid
	Y.7	0,693	Valid
	Y.8	0,818	Valid
	Y.9	0,793	Valid
	Y.10	0,744	Valid
	Y.11	0,801	Valid
	Y.12	0,744	Valid

Source: Primary data processed

Based on the validity test in Table 1 above, in the validity test, all questionnaire items are declared valid because all questionnaire items have correlation values greater than the required r value of 0.3.

Reliability Test

Table 2. The Result of Reliability Test

No	Variable	Cronbach's alpha	Description
1	Coordination (X1)	0,906	Reliable
2	Leadership Quality (X2)	0,957	Reliable
3	Work Discipline (Y)	0,963	Reliable

Source: Primary data processed.

Based on the results of the reliability test in this study, the reliability value of all instruments is accepted or reliable because it has a minimum Cronbach's Alpha and Cronbach's Alpha If Item Deleted values greater than the reliability standard, which is 0.6

Multiple Linear Regression

The testing was conducted with a confidence level of 95% or a significance level of 0.05 ($\alpha = 0.05$). To examine the validity of these hypotheses, multiple linear regression analysis was employed. In this regression analysis, both simultaneous or F-test and partial or t-test will be conducted.

Table 3. Multiple Linear Regression Test

Variable	Regression Coefficient (bi)	t count	t table	Beta	sig
Constant	8,009				
Coordination (X1)	0,577	3,129	1,993	0,368	0,003
Leadership Quality (X2)	0,290	3,379	1,993	0,369	0,001
Constant = 8,009		F count = 36,978			
Multiple R = 0,709		F table = 3,120			
R square (R ²) = 0,503		Sig = 0,000			

Source: Primary data processed.

In Table above, an R Square of 0.503 can be observed, indicating that 50.3% of the variation in the dependent variable is explained by the contributions of all independent variables. The remaining 49.7% is attributed to other factors beyond the scope of this study. Based on the obtained R2 in this research, which approaches 1 (one), it can be inferred that the relationship between independent and dependent variables is strong. When R2 approaches 1 (one), it is indicative of a stronger ability of the model to explain the relationship between independent and dependent variables. Conversely, as R2 approaches 0 (zero), the influence of independent variables on the dependent variable weakens.

According to Table 3, the regression equation is as follows:

$$Y = 8,009 + 0,577X1 + 0,290X2 + e$$

Based on the results of the equation above, it can be interpreted as follows:

1. If the coefficient of 0.577 for variable X1 (Coordination) increases, assuming the coefficient of 0.290 for variable X2 (Leadership Quality) remains constant, then Performance will also increase.
2. If the coefficient of 0.290 for variable X2 (Leadership Quality) increases, assuming the coefficient of 0.577 for variable X1 (Coordination) remains constant, then Performance will also increase.

Interpretation of the constant (8.009) in this study: Considering that the variables are measured on a Likert scale ranging from 1 to 5, it is not appropriate to interpret that if the values of Coordination (X1) and Leadership Quality (X2) are zero, as these variables

cannot take on a value of zero. The lowest Likert scale used is 1. Based on the SPSS calculations in this study, the constant value is 8.009, which falls into the category of good.

DISCUSSION

Based on the research results table, it can be observed that Coordination and Leadership Quality have a partial influence on the Work Discipline of employees in the Department of Food Security, Agriculture, and Fisheries of South Barito Regency. Coordination is crucial in an organization to ensure employee discipline in work through shared perceptions, unified actions, and effective communication among employees and with other work units. Respondents dominantly agreed that effective leadership involves organizing assigned tasks, ensuring harmony in achieving work results, coordinating within planned time, and communicating effectively in gathering and disseminating information. They also emphasized the importance of a clear organizational flow, the availability of information technology to facilitate communication, leaders distributing tasks to achieve organizational goals, providing detailed task assignments to all employees, and specialization in job distribution based on individual expertise.

The Leadership Quality variable significantly influences the Work Discipline of employees in the Department of Food Security, Agriculture, and Fisheries of South Barito Regency. Leadership plays a vital role in enhancing employee discipline, with firm and exemplary leaders influencing their subordinates to be disciplined in their work. Respondents predominantly strongly agreed that effective leaders can direct and supervise work, evaluate the work of employees, have a desire for success, and strive to advance the organization. Employees also perceive their leaders as wise, creative, innovative, capable of making good decisions without external influence, adept at problem-solving, quick decision-makers, able to face and solve problems, and always finding new ways to work efficiently. Additionally, leaders initiate building a comfortable work atmosphere and strive to ensure work efficiency.

Thus, the third hypothesis stating that Leadership Quality is the dominant variable influencing the Work Discipline of employees in the Department of Food Security, Agriculture, and Fisheries of South Barito Regency is invalid and not supported.

These research findings align with Sani's theory (2013:250), which emphasizes that effective leadership involves the ability to supervise and direct subordinates, a need for achievement in work, intelligence, decisiveness, self-confidence, and initiative. If leaders possess such qualities, employees are more likely to work with discipline as leaders can guide and supervise them effectively, including in terms of work discipline.

Based on the research results and analysis, the implications of the findings can be outlined as follows:

1. Continuous improvement in work discipline requires effective coordination in conveying the attendance system, performance targets, and discipline rules to all employees in the Department of Food Security, Agriculture, and Fisheries of South Barito Regency. This is crucial because the department has numerous employees and work units, necessitating strong coordination in the implementation of work discipline, particularly in unity of action and communication that needs enhancement. Unity of action involves a collective commitment to improving discipline in accordance with the rules, and communication is essential in disseminating discipline rules in the workplace.
2. Leaders can provide guidance to employees to consistently maintain discipline in their work by enforcing discipline rules and imposing fair sanctions on all employees in the Department of Food Security, Agriculture, and Fisheries of South Barito Regency. The role of leaders is essential in efforts to enhance work discipline by enforcing discipline rules for all employees in the department.

Therefore, effective coordination, unity of action, and communication are necessary for the continuous improvement of work discipline. Leaders play a crucial role in instilling discipline by enforcing rules and applying consistent sanctions to all employees in the Department of Food Security, Agriculture, and Fisheries of South Barito Regency.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the research and discussion, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. Coordination and Leadership Quality have a significant simultaneous effect on the Work Discipline of employees in the Food Security, Agriculture, and Fisheries Department of South Barito Regency.

2. Coordination and Leadership Quality have a significant partial effect on the Work Discipline of employees in the Food Security, Agriculture, and Fisheries Department of South Barito Regency.
3. The variable that dominantly influences the Work Discipline of employees in the Food Security, Agriculture, and Fisheries Department of South Barito Regency is Leadership Quality.

RECOMMENDATION

Based on the results of the discussion and conclusions, the recommendations from the results of this research are:

1. The research findings indicate that the Leadership Quality variable has a significant and dominant influence on the Work Discipline of employees in the Food Security, Agriculture, and Fisheries Department of South Barito Regency. Therefore, in the future, leaders must genuinely enforce continuous supervision on employees regarding disciplinary rules, ensure their adherence to regulations, apply strict sanctions to create a deterrent effect, and acknowledge and reward disciplined employees.
2. The Coordination variable also has a significant impact on the Work Discipline of employees in the Food Security, Agriculture, and Fisheries Department of South Barito Regency. In the future, this can be achieved by fostering effective coordination among all employees in the organization. Given that the department in this study has a diverse workforce, including field extension workers and office-based administrative staff, proper coordination is essential for implementing work discipline.

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